

A Binuclear Iron(III) Complex of *N,N,N',N'*-Tetrakis[(2-benzimidazolyl)]-1,2-ethanediamine

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A di-iron(III) complex of the hexadentate ligand *N,N,N',N'*-tetrakis[(2-benzimidazolyl)methyl]-1,2-ethanediamine has been synthesised. X-Band epr of the complex at 143 K reveals the presence of a isotropic $g \sim 4.3$ signal, its temperature dependence is indicative of a rapidly relaxing system. Electronic absorption spectrum of the complex shows a band at 330 nm which is assigned to $\text{Cl}^- \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$ low energy charge transfer transition, rather than a $\text{O}^2- \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$ C.T. band, a conclusion supported by a μ_{eff} /iron atom of 5.68 B.M. at 300 K, in DMSO- d_6 . The complex shows a reversible redox couple with $E_{1/2} = +0.315$ V. Reaction of catechol with the complex results in the diminishing of the $g \sim 4.3$ signal and the appearance of new signals at 780 and 1175 gauss in its X-band epr spectra. The optical spectrum shows a new broad band centred at 650 nm. This is interpreted in terms of binding of catechol to the iron centre, resulting in the transformation of a rhombic to a axially distorted iron complex. This complex may have relevance to iron coordination sites in catechol 1,2-dioxygenase, phenylalanine hydroxylase and methane mono-oxygenase.

There is a compelling interest in the synthesis and characterisation of di-iron complexes with multidentate ligands containing rigidly incorporated benzimidazole groups, as these ligands simulate a strained low symmetry environment as can be imposed by the protein backbone structure¹. Besides, the imidazole moiety also serves as a model for histidine residues that are found to bind active sites in di-iron metalloenzymes^{2,3}.

In the present study we have employed a hexadentate ligand capable of binding two iron atoms. Earlier work has established the suitability of this ligand for binuclear copper⁴ and manganese⁵ complexes.

Results and Discussion

Epr spectroscopy : Fig. 1 illustrates the 9.5 GHz epr spectrum of $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl}$ at 143 K, examined as a methanol solution. The complex shows a sharp intense transition centered at $g \sim 4.3$. An investigation of the temperature dependence of $g \sim 4.3$ signal was undertaken. Fig. 2 shows the change in the intensity of signal as the temperature is varied. No signal is observed above 200 K. The relative peak height of signal changes to as much as 80 times on going from 200 to 118 K and the line width narrowed dramatically from 250 gauss (peak to peak) to 12.5 gauss (peak to peak) in the same

Fig. 1. 10000 G scan of the $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl}$ at X-band; microwave power = 10 mW, microwave frequency = 9.20 GHz, 2.0 G modulation amplitude $T = 143$ K, receiver gain = 1.6×10^3 .

temperature range. A plot of $\log \delta$ (line-width) vs $1/T$ is depicted in Fig. 3. This shows a linear

Fig. 2. 5000 G scan of the $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl}$ complex centered at 2500 G; microwave power = 10 mW, microwave frequency = 9.2 GHz, 6.3 G modulation amplitude $T = 200$ K (receiver gain = 8×10^2), $T = 173$ K (receiver gain = 8×10^2), $T = 143$ K (receiver gain = 2×10^2), $T = 118$ K (receiver gain = 1×10^2).

relationship as is expected if the complex was undergoing rapid electron spin relaxation.

Magnetic susceptibility, electronic and ir spectroscopy: The solution magnetic susceptibility of $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl} \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex was determined by Evan's method⁷ at 300 K in DMSO-d_6 . The diamagnetic correction for this complex was estimated using Pascal's constants and has been incorporated in the experimental solution susceptibility. The magnetic moment for $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl} \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is found to be 5.68 B.M./atom (μ_{eff} for dimer is 8.03 B.M.).

Electronic spectrum of $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl} \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was taken in butanol. This shows uv spectra characteristic of the benzimidazolyl group.

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log \delta$ (line width) vs $1/T$ for $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl}$ complex.

Observed optical bands are at λ_{max} 240 ($\log \epsilon$ 3.96), 269 (4.04), 276 (4.05) and 330 nm (3.60). The uv bands are all blue-shifted upon coordination. The broad band at λ_{max} 246 nm in ligand which is associated with the imidazole ring, shows the largest shift to 240 nm in complex, showing clear evidence of C=N coordination to iron centre. A broad band is also observed at 330 nm ($\epsilon = 3981 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). This region has been normally called the iron-oxo dimer region⁸ as many of the iron-oxo dimeric complexes exhibit low energy charge transfer bands in this region⁹. However, Reem *et al.*¹⁰ elegantly demonstrated that bands at 300–400 nm may as well arise from exogenous ligands like OCN^- , Cl^- , CN^- etc. and based on their studies a band at 344 nm in met Cl^- hemerythrin is attributed to $\text{Cl}^- \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$ charge transfer transition¹⁰.

In our complex, we tend to assign the 330 nm band as arising due to $\text{Cl}^- \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$ low energy charge transfer transition rather than LMCT $\text{O}^{2-} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$ band. This is supported by the high μ_{eff} /iron atom in the complex, since oxo-bridged di-iron complexes have quite low μ_{eff} even at room temperatures owing to strong antiferromagnetic coupling¹¹.

The ir spectrum was taken in nujol mull. In the free ligand, a strong band appears at $1\ 435\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with two other weaker bands at around $1\ 445$ and $1\ 480\text{ cm}^{-1}$. On the basis of the analogy with the assigned bands for imidazole, the $1\ 435\text{ cm}^{-1}$ band is attributable to ν_s ($-\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{C}-$) while the other two are overtone or combination bands. In $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl}\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex, the $1\ 435\text{ cm}^{-1}$ band of ligand shifts to $1\ 450\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This implies direct coordination of all four imine nitrogen atoms to Fe^{II} . These are the preferred nitrogen atoms for coordination as found in other metal complexes with benzimidazoles¹².

Cyclic voltammetry : Fig. 4 depicts the cyclic voltammogram of the $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl}$ complex. The working electrode was Pt with a Pt counter

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl}$ complex 10^{-3} M in 1 : 4.5 methanol/acetonitrile; Tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (0.1 M) is supporting electrolyte, scan rate = 100 mV s^{-1} SCE.

electrode. In the complex a reversible oxidation wave is observed with a $E_{1/2}$ of $+0.315\text{ V}$. A subsequent oxidation step is then observed around 1 V for which no corresponding reduction wave is seen. We, therefore, tend to assign the first oxidation wave due to the conversion of one iron(III) to iron(IV) in the dimeric species $(\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}-\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}) \rightarrow (\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}-\text{Fe}^{\text{III}})$. The subsequent oxidation step observed at 1.0 V is most likely the process $(\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}-\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}) \rightarrow (\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}-\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}})$. It appears that the latter species is unstable and disproportionates on C.V. time-scale,

consequently no reduction wave for the process $(\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}-\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}) \rightarrow (\text{Fe}^{\text{IV}}-\text{Fe}^{\text{III}})$ is observed.

Fig. 5. (A) 5000 G scan centered at 2500 G of the $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl}$ complex; microwave power = 10 mW, microwave frequency = 9.2 GHz, modulation amplitude = 6.3 G, $T = 143\text{ K}$, receiver gain = 2×10^2 . (B) 5000 G scan centered at 2500 G of a mixture of $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl}$ and excess of catechol. Other condition identical to that in (A). (C) with receiver gain = 8×10^2 . (D) Visible spectrum of mixture of $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl}$ and excess of catechol; visible spectra of catechol (dotted line).

As a control we have also taken the voltammogram of FeCl_3 and it is found that it does not give any wave corresponding to potentials observed for the above complex. Ferrocene was used as an external standard and it is found that the peak to peak width is in the range 70–80 mV which is usually observed for a one-electron process. All potentials are with respect to SCE. On this basis we have assigned all the redox processes in the above complex as one-electron changes.

Reactivity towards catechol and TMPD : Fig. 5 depicts the change produced in the epr spectrum of the $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl}$ complex upon addition of

catechol. It is observed that under similar conditions of temperature, receiver gain, power etc., the $g \sim 4.3$ signal reduces in intensity by about five times (comparing peak heights only) when solid catechol is added to a solution of $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl}$ in methanol, while two new signals appear at 780 and 1175 gauss. This is also accompanied by the appearance of a broad band in the optical spectrum centering at about 650 nm. In this context it may be pointed out that high-spin ferric enzymes, catechol 1,2-dioxygenase and protocatechuate 3,4-dioxygenase, which catalyse the oxidative cleavage of catechols to *cis-cis* muconic acids^{13,14} upon binding of catechol introduce a new feature in the visible spectrum of the enzyme at 600–800 nm, which is assigned to catecholate-to- Fe^{III} charge transfer band. While another high-spin iron enzyme phenylalanine hydroxylase upon binding of catecholamines shifts the epr signals to a different

Fig. 6. Visible spectra of TMPD in presence of $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl}$: lower, time 10 min and upper, time 30 min.

E/D¹⁵. We, therefore, propose that binding of catechol takes place to the iron centre in the $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl}$ complex resulting in a smaller E/D for a more axially distorted catechol bound species, and thereby observation of new epr and optical bands. Reduction of the ferric centre does not occur as catecholate coordination is expected to stabilise the iron(III) state¹⁶.

The compound was also reacted with TMPD (tetramethylphenylenediamine) and it was found that oxidation of TMPD by molecular oxygen is

enhanced in the presence of the iron complex. This is depicted in Fig. 6, where it is seen that the bands at around 570 and 610 nm due to the formation of TMPD cation radical continue to grow with time. The spectra are all relative to a TMPD solution exposed to the same extent of time with molecular oxygen, with no $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl}$ complex present.

The above two experiments clearly indicate that the two iron atoms can be bound by exogenous ligands.

Fig. 7. Proposed structure of $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl}$ complex.

On the basis of these studies tentative structure of iron(III) complex is shown in Fig. 7.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade and used as received.

Preparation of $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{EDTB})\text{Cl}_5]\text{Cl} \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$: The ligand EDTB was prepared as reported earlier⁶. The ligand (0.33 mmol) was suspended in methanol and FeCl_3 solution (0.66 mmol; 0.5 ml) was added to the ligand. Most of the ligand went into solution and a very deep red colour was obtained. The solution was stirred for about 30 min at room temperature. The deep red solution was reduced to a small volume on rotatory evaporator and a small amount of ether was added to precipitate the crude product. The compound was purified by recrystallisation from methanol-ether mixture (1 : 5) to reddish yellow crystals on cooling (Found: C, 40.3; H, 3.8; N, 13.9; Fe, 10.9. Requires C, 40.3; H, 4.4; N, 13.8; Fe, 11.1%).

This preparative procedure resulted in the formation of a product which is entirely different from that reported earlier¹⁷.

IR spectra were taken on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 554 spectrophotometer, X-band epr spectra on a Jeol JES-Fe 3XG spectrometer with a variable temperature liquid nitrogen cryostat and ¹H nmr

spectra on a 90 MHz Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer. Cyclic voltammetric measurements were done on a PAR-173 with a PAR-175 instruments.

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